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CRITICAL REVIEW ON MADHAV DRAVYAGUNA

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Abstract

Nighantu is lexicon-graphical collection of *Vedic* works. *Nighantukara* compiled all the knowledge from *vedas* and *samhitas*, reformed them using rich literal heritage of *Sanskrit*, giving different names to same plant and same names to different plants. Also, incorporated their own experience and views in form of synonyms, properties, actions etc. In the tradition of *Ayurvedic Nighantu*, *Madhav Dravyaguna* is one of the important *Nighantu*. This work is of medieval period. It is composed by *Madhav Kavi* in 14th century. This *Nighantu* has 29 *Varga* described in detail. Classification and Arrangement of subject matter is more comprehensive in compare to other *Nighantus*. The objective of this work is to critically review *Madhav Dravyaguna Nighantu*.

Key Words:

Ayurveda, Dravyaguna, Madhav Dravyaguna, Nighantu

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INTRODUCTION:

Author of *Madhav Dravyaguna*:

The last verse of this work indicates that it is composed by *Madhava kavi*. After this, there is a sentence which shows that the work is read by *Mahadeva Misra* in the year 1509 (*Samvat*) which comes to 1452 A.D. This may be about the transcription of the work. *Srikantadatta*, *Chakradatta*, and *Madhav Pursottam* were Grandfather, father and son of *Maddhav Kavi* respectively¹.

Following are the authors and book who quoted *Madhavkavi's* work²:

Table No. 1 List of authors and book who quoted *Madhavkavi's* work

Author	Book	Period
Bopadeva	Siddhamantra	14th Century
Sivadasa Sen	-	15th Century
Adhmalla	-	15th -16th Century
Todarmala	Todaranand	16th Century
Sivadatta Misra	Sivakosa	17th Century
Swami Laxmi Ram	Siddha Bhaisajya Manimala	20th Century

Method of Presentation of Data:

Nighantu is divided into 29 *Varga* (Various classification groups), among it, *Vividha Ausadhi Varga* includes all the *Ausadha dravyas* both herbs and minerals. Minerals and animal products are described after herbs. It ends with description of *Puspa* (flowers) *Ausadha Dravyas* having common therapeutic effects are arranged one after the other. Ex: *Patha*, *Kutaja*, *Musta*, *Ativisha*, *Bilva* etc (Grahi action). *Lavana Varga* is placed at second position. *Sneha Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Ghrita* and *Taila Varga*. *Kanjika Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Madya Varga*. *Matsya Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Mamsa Varga*.

Vargas: There is total 29 *Vargas* told by *Acharya Madhav*. They are-

Table No.2 List of 29 *Vargas* described in *Madhav Dravyaguna*

1.	<i>Vividha Aushadhi Varga</i>	11.	<i>Sneha Varga</i>	21.	<i>Phala Varga</i>
2.	<i>Lavan Varga</i>	12.	<i>Madhya Varga</i>	22.	<i>Shaka Varga</i>
3.	<i>Ikshu Varga</i>	13.	<i>Kanjik Varga</i>	23.	<i>Srestha Varga</i>
4.	<i>Madhu Varga</i>	14.	<i>Mutra Varga</i>	24.	<i>Rasa Varga</i>
5.	<i>Kshira Varga</i>	15.	<i>Toya Varga</i>	25.	<i>Manda Varga</i>
6.	<i>Dadhi Varga</i>	16.	<i>Shali Varga</i>	26.	<i>Anna Varga</i>
7.	<i>Takra Varga</i>	17.	<i>Kudhanya Varga</i>	27.	<i>Panabhakshya Varga</i>
8.	<i>Navanita Varga</i>	18.	<i>Simbidhanya Varga</i>	28.	<i>Anupana Varga</i>
9.	<i>Ghruta Varga</i>	19.	<i>Mamsa Varga</i>	29.	<i>Prakirna Varga</i>
10.	<i>Taila Varga</i>	20.	<i>Matsya Varga</i>		

1-Vividha Aushadhi Varga: There are total 233 drugs mentioned in *Vividhaushadhi Varga*, it includes herbal and mineral drugs. They are

Table No.3 List of *Dravyas* described into *Vividha Aushadhi Varga*

Sanskrit Name	Latin / English Name	Sanskrit Name	Latin/ English Name
<i>Siva (Haritaki)</i>	<i>Terminalia Chebula Retz.</i>	<i>Sirisa</i>	<i>Albizzia lebbek Bent.</i>
<i>Dhatri</i>	<i>Phyllanthus embelica L.</i>	<i>Dhattura</i>	<i>Datura metel Linn.</i>

(Amalaki)			
Aksha (Vibhitaki)	<i>Terminalia belerica</i> Roxb.	Sikthaka	Wax
Trivrut	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso	Durva	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (Linn.) Pers.
Rajavruksha (Aragvadhya)	<i>Cassia fistula</i> Linn.	Nisa (Haridra)	<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn.
Trayanti	<i>Gentiana kurroo</i> Royle.	Darvi (Daruharidra)	<i>Berberis aristata</i> DC.
Yasa (Yavasa)	<i>Alhaghi pseudalhagi</i> (Bieb) Desv	Avalgujaphala	<i>Senna obtusifolia</i> (L.) Irwin &Barneby;
Bhudhatri (Bhumyamal aki)	<i>Phyllanthus fraternus</i> Webst.	Prapunata	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb.
Khadira	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (Linn.f.)Willd.	Karanja	<i>Milletia pinnata</i> (L.) Panigrahi;
Bhunimba	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Wall ex Nees	Kimsuka	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taubert;
Nimba	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss	Aristaphalam	<i>Sapindus trifoliatus</i> L.
Mahanimba	<i>Melia azedarach</i> Linn.	Vidanga	<i>Embelia ribes</i> Burm.f.
Parpatah	<i>Fumaria parviflora</i> Lam	Asphota	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L.
Patha	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> Linn	Tinisa	<i>Ougeinia dalbergioides</i> Benth.
Kutajah	<i>Holarrhena</i> <i>antidysentetica</i> (Roth) A.DC	Asana	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxb.
Hribera	<i>Coleus vettiveroides</i>	Simsapa	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> Roxb. Ex

	K.C.Jacob		DC.
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Cyperus rotandus</i> Linn.	<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (L.) Kurz;
<i>Ativisa Dvaya</i> (<i>Ativisa - Prativisa</i>)	<i>Aconitum heterophyllum</i> Wall.ex.Royle	<i>Kadara</i>	<i>Acacia polyacantha</i> Willd.
<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr.	<i>Aphuka</i> (<i>Ahiphena</i>),	<i>Papaver somniferum</i> L.
<i>Citraka</i>	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> Linn.	<i>Apamarga</i>	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> Roxb.
<i>Punarnava Yugma</i> (<i>Sveta Punarnava - Rakta Punarnava</i>)	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.; <i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	<i>Sinduvāra</i>	<i>Vitex negundo</i> Linn.
<i>Danti</i>	<i>Baliospermum montanum</i> Muell-Arg.	<i>Vansa</i>	<i>Bambusa arundinacea</i> (Retz.)Willd.
<i>Hastidanti</i>	<i>Croton roxburghii</i> Balak.	<i>Rohitaka</i>	<i>Tecomella undulata</i> (Sm.) Seem.
<i>Jayapala</i>	<i>Croton tiglium</i> L.	<i>Vruddhadaru</i>	<i>Argyrea nervosa</i> (Burm.f.) Boj.
<i>Snuhi</i>	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i> Linn.	<i>Bhurja</i>	<i>Betula utilis</i> D.Don.
<i>Hemahva</i>	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	<i>Tagara</i>	<i>Valeriana wallichii</i> DC.
<i>Arka</i>	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) R.Br.	<i>Kaunti</i>	-
<i>Aruskara</i> (<i>Bhallātaka</i>)	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> Linn.	<i>Satahvadi</i> <i>Dravya</i>	-

<i>Guggulu</i>	<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.) Bhand.	<i>Srivasadi Dravya</i>	-
<i>Lasuna</i>	<i>Allium sativum</i> Linn.	<i>Chandana</i>	<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.
<i>Palandu</i>	<i>Allium cepa</i> L.	<i>Lohitacandana (Raktacandan)</i>	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> L.f.
<i>Kshirapalan du</i>	<i>Allium wallichii</i> Kunth	<i>Patanga</i>	<i>Caesalpinia sappan</i> L.
<i>Grunjanaka</i>	<i>Daucus carota</i> L.	<i>Padmaka – Sevya</i>	<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> D.Don.
<i>Ardraka</i>	<i>Zinziber officinale</i> Rosc.	<i>Kunkuma</i>	<i>Crocus sativus</i> Linn.
<i>Gandiradi guna</i>	-	<i>Kasturi</i>	<i>Moschus mosciferus</i> L.
<i>Nagara (Sunthi)</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Rosc.	<i>Aguru</i>	<i>Aquilaria agallocha</i> Roxb.
<i>Pippali</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	<i>Suradaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i> (Roxb.) Loud
<i>Pippalimula</i>	<i>Piper longum</i> Linn.	<i>Katruna</i>	<i>Cymbopogon citrates</i> (DC) Stapf
<i>Marica</i>	<i>Piper nigrum</i> Linn.	<i>Kankola</i>	<i>Piper cubeba</i> L.f.
<i>Cavika</i>	<i>Piper retrofractum</i> Vahl.	<i>Jatiphala</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.
<i>Gajapippali</i>	<i>Scindapsus officinalis</i> Schoott	<i>Lavangakusum a</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (Linn.) Merr M.Perry.
<i>Hingu</i>	<i>Ferula foetida</i> Regel.	<i>Jatikosa</i>	<i>Myristica fragrans</i> Houtt.
<i>Jirakadvaya</i>	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i> ; <i>Carum carvi</i> Linn.	<i>Karpura</i>	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> (L.) Nees& Embem.

<i>Karavi</i>	<i>Carum bulbocastunum</i>	<i>Bhanga</i>	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> Linn.
<i>Upakuncika</i>	<i>Nigella sativa</i> Linn.	<i>Ela</i>	<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (Linn.)
<i>Baspika</i>	<i>Nigella sativa</i> Linn.	<i>Lavanga</i>	<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> (Linn.) Merr M. Perry.
<i>Rajika</i>	<i>Brassica juncea</i> (L.) Czern.	<i>Caksusya</i>	<i>Cassia absus</i> L.
<i>Bhustrna</i>	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC. Ex Nees)	<i>Latakasturika</i>	<i>Hibiscus abelmoschus</i> Linn.
<i>Kharahva</i>	<i>Apium leptophyllum</i> (Pers.) F.V.M.ex Benth.	<i>Katphala</i>	<i>Myrica esculenta</i> Buch-Ham. Ex.D.Don
<i>Dhanyaka,</i>	<i>Coriandrum sativum</i> L.	<i>Satahva</i>	<i>Anethum sowa</i> Roxb.ex Flem.
<i>Bhanga</i>	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	<i>Phalini</i>	-
<i>Jambira</i>	<i>Citrus limon</i> (L.) Burm.f. (pro sp.)	<i>Gandhapriyan gu</i>	<i>Calicarpa macrophylla</i> Vahl.
<i>Surabhi</i>	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolate</i> Oliver & Hiem.
<i>Surasa (Tulasi)</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i> Linn.	<i>Pauskaram(Pu skaramulam)</i>	<i>Inula racemose</i> Hook.f
<i>Krsnagandha (Sigru)</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam	<i>Sati</i>	<i>Hedychium spicatum</i> Ham. Ex.Smith.
<i>Madhusigru</i>	<i>Moringa concanensis</i> Nimmo Ex Dalz. & Gibson	<i>Madana</i>	<i>Xeromphis spinose</i> Thunb) Keay.
<i>Varuna</i>	<i>Crateva religiosa</i> G. Forst.	<i>Srungi</i>	-
<i>Paribhadra</i>	<i>Erythrina indica</i> Lam.	<i>Varanga</i>	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> Blume
<i>Bilva mula</i>	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corr.	<i>Nagakhesara</i>	<i>Messua ferrea</i>

	Serr.		
<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum chelonoides</i> (L.F) DC	<i>Patraka</i>	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> (Buch-Ham) Nees & Embem.
<i>Katvanga</i> (<i>Syonaka</i>)	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> Vent.	<i>Talisapatra</i>	<i>Abies webbiana</i> Lindl.
<i>Kasmaryam</i> (<i>Gambhari</i>)	<i>Gmelina arbora</i> Roxb.	<i>Vamsarocana -</i> <i>Tugaksiri</i>	<i>Bambusa arundinaceae</i> Willd.
<i>Vahnimantha</i> (<i>Agnimanth</i>)	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> Linn.	<i>Vasa</i>	<i>Adhatoda Vasica</i> Nees.
<i>Eranda mula</i>	<i>Ricinus communis</i> Linn.	<i>Kumari</i>	<i>Aloe barbadensis</i> Mill.
<i>Trikanṭaka</i> (<i>Gokshura</i>)	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> Linn.	<i>Amruta</i>	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers.
<i>Kantakarika</i>	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm.f.	<i>Maksika Dhatu</i>	<i>Copper pyrites</i>
<i>Bruhati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum</i> Linn.	<i>Silajatu</i>	Black bitumen
<i>Prusnaparni</i>	<i>Uria picta</i> Desv.	<i>Gairika</i>	Red oxide of iron
<i>Sthira</i> (<i>Salaparni</i>)	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> DC	<i>Tuttha</i>	Copper sulphate
<i>Balatrayam</i> (<i>Bala -</i> <i>Mahabala -</i> <i>Nagabala</i>)	<i>Bala - Sida cordifolia</i> L.; <i>Mahabala - Sida rhombifolia</i> Linn.; <i>Nagabala - Sida cordata</i> (Burm. f.) Waalkes	<i>Haratala</i>	Orpiment
<i>Ashwagandha</i>	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal.	<i>Anjanam</i>	Stybnite
<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> W. & A.	<i>Parada</i>	Mercury

<i>Masaparni</i>	<i>Teramnus labialis</i> Spreng.	<i>Abhraka</i>	Mica
<i>Mudgaparni</i>	<i>Phaseolus radiatus</i> Linn.	<i>Hingula</i>	Cinnabar
<i>Ruddhi – Vruddhi</i>	<i>Habenaria intermedia</i> Don.	<i>Gandhaka</i>	Sulphur
<i>Kakoliyugma (Kakoli - Ksirakakoli)</i>	Kakoli - <i>Lilium polyphyllum</i> D.Don. ; Kshirakakoli - <i>Fritillaria royelei</i> Hook.	<i>Shvetamarica (Seeds of Sigrū)</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.
<i>Jivaka- Rusabhaka</i>	Jivaka - <i>Malaxis acuminata</i> D.Don.	<i>Pitarohiṇi</i>	-
<i>Medayugma m (Meda - Mahameda)</i>	<i>Polygonatum cirrhifolium</i> Royle.	<i>Vandaka</i>	<i>Vanda roxburghii</i> R.BR.
<i>Vishala</i>	<i>Citrullus colocynthis</i> (L.) Schrad.	<i>Kasisadvaya</i>	Ferrous sulphate
<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (Linn.) R.Br.	<i>Laghusankha</i>	-
<i>Ananta</i>	<i>Alhagi camelorum</i> Fisch.	<i>Sankha</i>	-
<i>Gundra</i>	<i>Typha australis</i> Schum.and Thonn.	<i>Pravala</i>	-
<i>Lodhra - Savara Lodhra</i>	<i>Symplocos racemosa</i> Roxb.	<i>Maniratna</i>	-
<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i> L.	<i>Suvarna</i>	Gold
<i>Prapaundari ka</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.	<i>Roupya</i>	Silver

<i>Manjistha</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> Linn	<i>Tamra</i>	Copper
<i>Laksa</i>	Lac	<i>Kamsya</i>	Bronze
<i>Musali</i>	<i>Asparagus adscendens</i> Roxb.	<i>Trapu-Sisa</i>	Tin and Lead
<i>Satavari</i>	<i>Asparagus officinalis</i> L.	<i>Krusnayasa</i>	Iron
<i>Partha (Arjuna)</i>	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> W& A.	<i>Sindura</i>	Red sulphide of mercury
<i>Asthisamhar a</i>	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> Linn.	<i>Saurastri</i>	Alum
<i>Markava (Bhrigaraja)</i>	<i>Eclipta alba</i> Hassk	<i>Panka</i>	-
<i>Dronapuspik a</i>	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i> Spreng.	<i>Hastimada</i>	-
<i>Girikarnika (Aarajita)</i>	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Linn.	<i>Sarpapitta</i>	-
<i>Vruschikali</i>	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	<i>Gorocana</i>	Gall stones of cow
<i>Dugdika</i>	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	<i>Padma (Lotus)</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.
<i>Ahimsra</i>	<i>Capparis sepiaria</i> L.	<i>Bakula</i>	<i>Mimusops elengi</i> L.
<i>Sudarsana</i>	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	<i>Punnaga</i>	<i>Calophyllum inophyllum</i> L.
<i>Phanji</i>	<i>Clerodendron serratum</i> Linn.	<i>Kahlara</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.
<i>Gunja</i>	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> Linn.	<i>Utpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea stellata</i> Willd.
<i>Jayanti</i>	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> W. & A.	<i>Patala</i>	<i>Stereospermum chelonoides</i> (L.F) DC.
<i>Sairiya</i>	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> Linn.	<i>Champaka</i>	<i>Michelia champaca</i> L.
<i>Prasarani</i>	<i>Paedaria foetida</i> Linn.	<i>Kauranta</i>	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.

<i>Kokilaksha</i>	<i>Asteracantha longifolia</i> Nees.	<i>Kimsuka</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i> (Lam.) Taubert.
<i>Kulahala</i>	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	<i>Kumuda</i>	<i>Nymphaea alba</i> L.
<i>Halani</i>	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	<i>Saṇa</i>	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L.
<i>Karavira</i>	<i>Nerium indicum</i> Mill.	<i>Kovidara</i>	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i> Blume.
<i>Kukurunda</i>	-	<i>Karbudara</i>	<i>Bauhinia acuminata</i> L.
<i>Nagadamani</i>	<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	<i>Salmali</i>	<i>Salmalia malabarica</i> Schott & Endl.
<i>Avarttaki</i>	<i>Cassia auriculata</i> L.	<i>Bandhuka</i>	<i>Pentapetes phoenicea</i> L.
<i>Koshataki</i>	<i>Luffa acutangula</i> (Linn) Roxb.	<i>Yuthika</i>	<i>Jasminum auriculatum</i> Vahl.
<i>Jyotismati</i>	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd.	<i>Dhatakikusum</i> a	<i>Woodfordia floribunda</i> Salisb.
<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (Linn.) Wettst.	<i>Mucakunda</i>	<i>Pterospermum acerifolium</i> Willd.
<i>Vaca</i>	<i>Acorus calamus</i> Linn.	<i>Mallika</i>	<i>Jasminum sambac</i> (L.) Aiton
<i>Sankhapuspi</i>	<i>Convolvulus pluricaulis</i> Choisy.	<i>Japa</i>	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.
<i>Malati</i>	<i>Jasminum officinale</i> L.	<i>Vrusaga</i>	-
<i>Ketaka</i>	<i>Pandanus tectorius</i> Parkinson ex Zucc.		

Mishrak Gana described here are as following-

Table No.4 Mishrak Dravyas described into Vividha Aushadhi Varga

<i>Triphala</i>	1-Haritaki, 2-Amalaki, 3- Vibhitaki
<i>Trayusna</i>	1-Pipali, 2- Sunthi, 3-Marich
<i>Pancakola</i>	1-Pipali, 2- Pipalimoola, 3-Chavya, 4- Chitrak, 5- Nagara
<i>Sadusana</i>	1-Pipali, 2- Pipalimoola, 3-Chavya, 4- Chitrak, 5- Nagara, 6- Maricha
<i>Astavarga</i>	1-Rddhi, 2-Vrddhi, 3-Kakoli, 4-Kshirakakoli, 5-Jivaka, 6- Rushabhaka, 7- Meda, 8-Mahameda

While describing types of the *Dravya* like *Punarnava Yugma*, it is described that both *Punarnava* types (*Shweta* and *Rakta Punarnava*) are having same properties, same with *Bala Traya*, *Kakoli Yugma*, *Meda Yugma*, etc. Drugs having same functions are described one after another (ex. *Grahi Dravya*, *Virechaka Dravya*).

Drugs having similar properties are described together in one verse like in *Gandiradi Dravya*, *Shreevasadi Dravya* etc. Where *Gandira*, *Jalapipali*, *Tumburu* etc drug's properties are described as same.

Gandiradi Dravya includes-

Table No.5 List of Dravyas described into Gandiradi Dravya

<i>Gandira</i>	<i>Jalapipali</i>
<i>Tumbura</i>	<i>Shrungavera</i>

Shreevasadi Dravya includes-

Table No.6 List of *Dravyas* described into *Shreevasadi Dravya*

<i>Srivasa</i>	<i>Sarala</i>	<i>Bola</i>
<i>Kundururu</i>	<i>Granthiparni</i>	<i>Turuska</i>
<i>Sihlak</i>	<i>Sprukka</i>	<i>Gundra</i>
<i>Sarja</i>	<i>Mura</i>	<i>Nakh</i>

Two different drugs having similar properties are also described together as *Prushnaparni* and *Sthira* while in other *Nighantu* both drugs are described separately with their respective description of *Rasa*, *Guna* and *Roghagnata*.

In this *Nighantu* following *Dravyas* are described together due to their similar properties:

Cavika- Gajapipali, Karavi-Upkunchika, Ahimsra- Sudarshana, Halani-Karavira, Jatiphala-Lavangkusum, Bakul-punnaga-kalhar-utpal-patala-campaka, Kauranta-Kimshuka, Kumuda-utpala, Sana-Kovidara-Karbudara-Salmali flowers and Bandhuka- Uthika.

2-*Lavana Varga*⁴-

Here general properties of salts are given and then individually properties of 9 *Lavana* are described. List of *Lavana* described here are as following-

Table No. 7 List of *Dravyas* described into *Lavana Varga*

<i>Saindhava Lavana</i>	<i>Samudra Lavana</i>	<i>Bida Lavana</i>
<i>Sauvarchala Lavana</i>	<i>Krushna Lavana</i>	<i>Romaka Lavana</i>
<i>Audbhida Lavana</i>	<i>Gutika Lavana</i>	<i>Pamsuja Lavana</i>

Krushna Lavana, Gutika Lavana and *Pansuja Lavana* are additional contribution of *Madhav Kavi*, afterwards properties of various *Kshara* are described.

3- *Ikshu Varga*⁵ -

Here general properties of sugarcane are given and then types of sugarcane are describes with properties of sugarcane based on the part, preparations of *Ikshu* like *Guda* and *Sharakara* with different types described. Types of sugarcane described here are-

Table No.8 List of *Dravyas* described into *Ikshu Varga*

<i>Pundraka</i>	<i>Bhiruka</i>	<i>Vamsaka</i>	<i>Sataponaka</i>	<i>Kantar</i>
<i>Ikshu</i>	<i>Tapaseksu</i>	<i>Kandekshu</i>	<i>Suchipatra</i>	<i>Nepala</i>
<i>Dirgapatra</i>	<i>Nalapora</i>	<i>Keshakruta</i>		

Roots of *Iksu* are sweet in taste, internodes are sweet and the tips, nodes and bark of are salty in taste as described here by *Madhav Kavi*.

4- *Madhu Varga*⁶-

Types of honey, appearance of different types of honey, general properties of honey, and incompatibilities of honey (ex. along with hot substances, in patients suffering from diseases arising because of excessive *Ushna*) are described. Types of *Madhu* described here are-

Table No.9 List of *Dravyas* described into *Madhu Varga*

<i>Pautika</i>	<i>Bhramara</i>	<i>Kshaudra</i>	<i>Makshika</i>
<i>Chatra</i>	<i>Ardhya</i>	<i>Audalak</i>	<i>Dala</i>

Appearance of different types of honey as described here are- *Mākṣika* is similar in appearance to sesame oil (*Taila*), *Pautika* appears like *Ghee* (*Ghrīta*), *Kṣaudra* is tawny brown in colour (*Kapila Varna*) and *Bhramara* is clear like crystal (*Sphatika*).

5- *Kshira Varga*⁷-

Types of milk, properties of the milk obtained from cows having different colours, properties of hot and cold milk, properties of milk consumed at different times of the day, properties of the milk collected during different times of the day and properties of the milk that is not indicated for consumption are described here.

Types of milk described here are-

Table No. 10 List of *Dravyas* described into *Kshira Varga*

<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Aurabhra</i>	<i>Mahish</i>
<i>Karabh</i>	<i>Ashwa</i>	<i>Nari</i>	<i>Hasti</i>

Table No. 11 Properties of hot and cold milk

<i>Kshira</i> (Process)	Properties
<i>Shruta-ushna</i> (hot boiled)	<i>Kaphavataghna</i>
<i>Shruta-shita</i> (boiled and cooled)	<i>Pittajita</i>
<i>Ama</i> (not boiled)	<i>Amakara</i>
<i>Dharoshna</i>	<i>Amruta</i>

Table No.12 Properties of the milk collected during different times of the day

Milk Collection Time	Effect
Morning	Heavy (<i>Guru</i>), Constipating (<i>Vistambhi</i>) and Cool (<i>Sita</i>)
Afternoon (<i>Aparahnikam</i>)	Reduces <i>Vata, Pitta</i> , Fatigue (<i>Srama</i>) and improves vision (<i>Caksusya</i>)

Table No.13 Properties of milk consumed at different times of the day

Milk Intake Time	Effect
<i>Purvahnakale</i> (Forenoon)	Aphrodisiac (<i>Vrsya</i>), Nourisher (<i>Brmhana</i>), Appetizer (<i>Agnidipana</i>).
<i>Madhyahna</i> (Midnoon)	Increases strength (<i>Balavardhana</i>), Aphrodisiac (<i>Ratikara</i>) and increases libido (<i>Kamagni</i>).
<i>Ratri</i> (Night)	Acts as wholesome diet (<i>Pathya</i>), improves vision (<i>Caksusya</i>) and reduces many <i>Doṣa</i> .

6- Dadhi Varga⁸-

General properties of curd, different forms of the curds and their properties, indication of curd, contraindication of curd and complication of injudicious intake of curds are described.

Types of *Dadhi* described here are-

Table No.14 Types of *Dadhi* described into *Dadhi Varga*

<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Mahish</i>	<i>Austra</i>
<i>Badava (horse)</i>	<i>Naga (Elephant)</i>	<i>Nari</i>	<i>Avika</i>

7- Takra Varga⁹-

General properties of buttermilk, properties of buttermilk devoid of butter, properties of the buttermilk based on the taste, indications of buttermilk, properties of different form of buttermilk, different variants of the buttermilk and their properties and importance of daily intake of buttermilk are described in this *Varga*.

Table No.15 Properties of buttermilk of various types

Sr. No.	<i>Takra Prakara</i> (Type of Buttermilk)	Properties
1.	<i>Samudhrutghruta Takra</i> (Total butter is separated from buttermilk)	<i>Laghu, Pathya</i>
2.	<i>Ardhudhrutaghruta Takra</i> (Half butter is separated from buttermilk)	<i>Guru, Vrushya</i>
3.	<i>Anuddhrutghruta Takra</i> (Buttermilk with <i>Ghee</i>)	<i>Vrushyatama</i>

Table No.16 Properties of buttermilk of based on the taste

Sr. No.	<i>Takra Prakara</i> (Type of Buttermilk)	Properties
1.	<i>Amla</i>	<i>Tanu</i>
2.	<i>Atyamla</i>	<i>Sandra</i>
3.	<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Sandratarā</i>
4.	<i>Madhura</i>	<i>Guru</i>

8-Navanita Varga¹⁰-

Properties of freshly prepared butter, butter prepared from milk and types of butter are described in this *Varga*. Types of butter are similar to the types of the milk.

Table No.17 Types of *Navanita* described into *Navanita Varga*

<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Mahish</i>	<i>Austra</i>
<i>Badava (horse)</i>	<i>Naga (Elephant)</i>	<i>Nari</i>	<i>Avika</i>

9- *Ghruta Varga*¹¹-

General properties of *Ghruta*, individual properties of different type of *Ghruta*, different forms of *Ghruta* and their properties are described.

Types of *Ghruta* described here are-

Table No.18 Types of *Ghruta* described into *Ghruta Varga*

<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Mahish</i>	<i>Austra</i>
<i>Badava (horse)</i>	<i>Naga (Elephant)</i>	<i>Nari</i>	<i>Avika</i>

10- Taila Varga¹²-

General properties of oils and properties of various oils are described here.

Various oils described are as following-

Table No.19 List of *Dravyas* described into *Taila Varga*

<i>Tila</i>	<i>Kshauma</i>	<i>Sarsapa</i>	<i>Eranda</i>	<i>Kusumbh</i>
<i>Koshamra</i>	<i>Danti</i>	<i>Mulaka</i>	<i>Rakshogna</i>	<i>Karanja</i>
<i>Aristha</i>	<i>Sigru</i>	<i>Suvarchala</i>	<i>Ingudi</i>	<i>Pilu</i>
<i>Sankhini</i>	<i>Nipa</i>	<i>Sarala</i>	<i>Aguru</i>	<i>Devahva</i>
<i>Simsapa</i>	<i>Tuvaraak</i>	<i>Arushka</i>	<i>Karanja</i>	<i>Aristha</i>
<i>Saaral</i>	<i>Tuvara</i>	<i>Arushkara</i>	<i>Aksha</i>	<i>Atimuktak</i>
<i>Kshoda</i>	<i>Narikela</i>	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Trapusha</i>	<i>Airvaru</i>
<i>Kusmanda</i>	<i>Sleshmantak</i>	<i>Piyala</i>	<i>Shreeparni</i>	<i>Kimsuka</i>
<i>Yavabimbi</i>	<i>Sahakara</i>			

11- Sneha Varga¹³-

Properties of *Vasā* and *Majja*, *Vasa* obtained from different animals, *Grahya* and *Agrahya Vasā* are described in *Sneha Varga*.

12-Madya Varga¹⁴ -

General properties of alcoholic beverages (*Madya*), properties of different alcoholic preparations, properties of newly prepared *Madya*, properties of old and preserved *Madya*, *Vrjya Madya*, ill- effects of consuming contraindicated alcohols (*Vrjya Madya*) and properties of best alcohols are described here.

Different alcoholic preparations described are as following-

Table No.20 List of *Dravyas* described into *Taila Varga*

<i>Sura</i>	<i>Prassana</i>	<i>Yava</i>	<i>Madhulika</i>	<i>Kohala</i>
<i>Jagala</i>	<i>Bakkasa</i>	<i>Mardvika</i>	<i>Kharjura</i>	<i>Gauda</i>
<i>Sarkara</i>	<i>Pakwarasa</i>	<i>Sheetarasika</i>	<i>Madhvasava</i>	<i>Surasava</i>
<i>Akshika</i>	<i>Jambava</i>	<i>Mireyaka</i>	<i>Ikshurasava</i>	<i>Madhuka</i>

13- *Kanjika Varga*¹⁵⁻

Properties of *Sukta*, *Asuta*, *Sauvirak*, *Tushodaka*, *Amlakanji*, *Dhanyamla*, *Tushambu*; properties of *Kāñjika* administered for *Gandūṣa* and properties of *Kāñjika* are described in this *Varga*.

14- *Mutra Varga*¹⁶

Types of urine and their general properties and properties of various types of urine are described in this *Varga*.

Table No.21 List of *Dravyas* described into *Mutra Varga*

<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Mahish</i>	<i>Austra</i>	<i>Badava</i> (Horse)
<i>Naga</i> (Elephant)	<i>Manush</i>	<i>Avika</i>	<i>Gardabh</i>	

15- *Toya Varga*¹⁷

General properties of water, properties of boiled water, properties of water obtained from different sources, properties of water flowing from various directions, properties of the water based on the *Desa*, properties of water based on the rate of flow, contraindicated water, properties of hot water, properties of the water consumed at different times during food intake, properties of water flowing in different directions, different methods of boiling water in different seasons, definition of *Usnodaka*, changes in properties of water by boiling, indications of cold water, contraindications of cold water, coconut water and its properties, properties of water consumed at different times of digestion, properties of unboiled and boiled water, excessive drinking of water and, indications of excessive drinking of water and importance of water is described in this *Varga*.

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16-Shali Varga¹⁸

Various types of *Shali* are with their properties are described here. Various types of *Shali* described here are-

Table No.22 List of *Dravyas* described into *Shali Varga*

<i>Raktashali</i>	<i>Gaurshali</i>	<i>Mahashali</i>
<i>Kalama</i>	<i>Vrihi</i>	<i>Patala</i>

17- *Kudhanya Varga*¹⁹

Properties of various *Kudhanya* are described here. Various types of *Kudhanya* described here are-

Table No.23 List of *Dravyas* described into *Kudhanya Varga*

<i>Yavanala</i>	<i>Nivara</i>	<i>Syamaka</i>
<i>Kangu</i>	<i>Kordusha</i>	<i>Yava</i>
<i>Godhuma</i>	<i>Tila</i>	

Among *Kudhanya* *Godhum* and *Tila* are described here as *Kudhanya*.

18- *Simbidhanya Varga*²⁰

General properties of *Sukadhanyam* and *Samidhanyam*, conditions to obtain good quality grains, *Navadhanya* and *virudhdhanya Guna*.

List of *Dravyas* described here are-

Table No.24 List of *Dravyas* described into *Simbidhanya Varga*

<i>Mudga</i>	<i>Masura</i>	<i>Makusthaka</i>	<i>Canaka</i>
<i>Satina</i>	<i>Adhaki</i>	<i>Kalaya</i>	<i>Kulattha</i>
<i>Vanyakulattha</i>	<i>Masa</i>	<i>Rajamasa</i>	<i>Kukanda</i>
<i>Atmagupta</i>	<i>Kusumbha</i>	<i>Nispava</i>	<i>Sarshapa</i>

19-*Mamsa Varga*²¹

Types of meat, properties of the meat from different portions of the body, properties of the meat from different herbivorous and carnivorous animals are described in this *Varga*. List of various *Mamsa* described here are-

Table No.25 List of *Dravyas* described into *Mamsa Varga*

<i>Aina</i>	<i>Harina</i>	<i>Sasah</i>	<i>Aja</i>	<i>Aurabhra</i>
<i>Gavya</i>	<i>Mahisha</i>	<i>Varah</i>	<i>Khadgi</i>	<i>Lava</i>
<i>Tittir</i>	<i>Gaurtittir</i>	<i>Krakara</i>	<i>Upchakrak</i>	<i>Barhi</i>
<i>Kapinjala</i>	<i>Paravat</i>	<i>Chitrang</i>	<i>Harita</i>	<i>Kukkuta</i>
<i>Kulinga</i>	<i>Vesmakulinga</i>	<i>Hamsa</i>	<i>Sarika</i>	<i>Godha</i>
<i>Musaka</i>	<i>Sarpa</i>	<i>Darvika</i>	<i>Sankh</i>	<i>Kurma</i>
<i>Krusnakarkatak</i>				

20- *Matsya Varga*²²

Various types of *Matsya* with *Guna*, *Matsya*, *Kūrma* and *Khaga Anda*, properties of the meat collected from different parts of the body are described in this *Varga*. List of various *Matsya* described here are-

Table No.26 List of *Dravyas* described into *Matsya Varga*

<i>Rohita</i>	<i>Nandikavarta</i>	<i>Shruni</i>	<i>Madguru</i>	<i>Sakula</i>
<i>Gomatsya</i>	<i>Ali</i>	<i>Trikantaka</i>	<i>Kantaka</i>	<i>Guru</i>
<i>Hilisa</i>	<i>Chadang</i>	<i>Kshudra</i>		

21-Phala Varga²³

Properties of various fruits are described here. Various fruits described here are-

Table No.27 List of *Dravyas* described into *Phala Varga*

<i>Dadima</i>	<i>Kshirivruksha phala</i>	<i>Parushaka</i>	<i>Tinduka</i>	<i>Jambu</i>
<i>Jambava</i>	<i>Rajajambu</i>	<i>Kshudrajambu</i>	<i>Nipa</i>	<i>Satalukam</i>
<i>Pilu</i>	<i>Trunashunya</i>	<i>Karkandhu</i>	<i>Kola</i>	<i>Badara</i>
<i>Vala</i>	<i>Pakwamra</i>	<i>Dugdhamra</i>	<i>Suskamra</i>	<i>Amrata</i>
<i>Panasa</i>	<i>Lakucha</i>	<i>Karmardak</i>	<i>Tintidika</i>	<i>Amrika</i>
<i>Airavat</i>	<i>Naranga</i>	<i>Amlavetasa</i>	<i>Matulunga</i>	<i>Madhukarkatika</i>
<i>Jambira</i>	<i>Nimbuka</i>	<i>Rajanambu</i>	<i>Karmaranga</i>	<i>Lavali</i>
<i>Parpataki</i>	<i>Mudwika</i>	<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Madhuka kusuma</i>	<i>Kapittha</i>
<i>Kaseruka</i>	<i>Srungatak</i>	<i>Grunjanak</i>	<i>Palandu</i>	<i>Karjura</i>
<i>Chara</i>	<i>Priyala</i>	<i>Tala</i>	<i>Narikela</i>	<i>Mocha</i>
<i>Kadali</i>	<i>Shleshmatak</i>	<i>Bakula</i>	<i>Paushkar</i>	<i>Kasmarya</i>
<i>Ashwattha</i>	<i>Udumbara</i>	<i>Plaksha</i>	<i>Nyagrodha</i>	<i>Audumbara</i>
<i>Vibhitaka</i>	<i>Amalaka</i>	<i>Bijapuraka</i>	<i>Sampaka-majja</i>	<i>Koshamra</i>
<i>Tuta</i>	<i>Amruta</i>	<i>Anjira</i>	<i>Akshoda</i>	<i>Alluka</i>
<i>Vatam</i>				

22- Saka Varga²⁴

Types of *Saka*, general properties of *Saka* and Various *Saka* with their properties are described in this *Varga*. Various *Saka* described here are-

Table No.28 List of *Dravyas* described into *Saka Varga*

<i>Jivanti</i>	<i>Tanduliyak</i>	<i>Vastuka</i>	<i>Chilli</i>	<i>Kasamarda</i>
<i>Kakamachi</i>	<i>Kakajangha</i>	<i>Methika</i>	<i>Satinaka</i>	<i>Harimanthaj</i>
<i>Kalaya</i>	<i>Rajakshavak</i>	<i>Mandukaparni</i>	<i>Gojihwa</i>	<i>Sunishnnak</i>
<i>Changeri</i>	<i>Kanchat</i>	<i>Maudaka</i>	<i>Varuna</i>	<i>Prapunnata</i>
<i>Vatsadani</i>	<i>Bilwapatra</i>	<i>Shreyasi</i>	<i>Tilaparni</i>	<i>Gandira</i>
<i>Chitraka</i>	<i>Kalashaka</i>	<i>Varshabhu</i>	<i>Venu</i>	<i>Karira</i>
<i>Atarushaka</i>	<i>Vetragra</i>	<i>Guduchi</i>	<i>Nimba</i>	<i>Parpata</i>
<i>Kirata</i>	<i>Kalinga</i>	<i>Vruntaka</i>	<i>Bruhati</i>	<i>Patola</i>
<i>Karvellaka</i>	<i>Chichinda</i>	<i>Veshmakola</i>	<i>Karkataki</i>	<i>Gruhapatolika</i>
<i>Kusmanda</i>	<i>Tumba</i>	<i>Karkota</i>	<i>Airvaru</i>	<i>Dimdisa</i>
<i>Trapusabeeja</i>	<i>Kusmanda</i>	<i>Alabu</i>	<i>Katutumbi</i>	<i>Trapusa</i>
<i>Eravaruka</i>	<i>Upodika</i>	<i>Aruka</i>	<i>Koshataki</i>	<i>Rajakoshataki</i>
<i>Mahakoshataki</i>	<i>Kalasiambi</i>	<i>Simbi</i>	<i>Dodika</i>	<i>Marusha</i>
<i>Marisha</i>	<i>Kalambu</i>	<i>Hilamochika</i>	<i>Brahmi</i>	<i>Grishmasundara</i>
<i>Mulaka</i>	<i>Potika</i>	<i>Sarsapa</i>	<i>Rajika</i>	<i>Kusumbha</i>
<i>Mashaparna</i>	<i>Shreehasti</i>	<i>Nyagrodha</i>	<i>Udumbara</i>	<i>Ashwattha</i>
<i>Plaksha</i>	<i>Padma</i>	<i>Chatraka</i>	<i>Palalekshu</i>	<i>Karira</i>
<i>Kshitivenuja</i>	<i>Kuvakutanda</i>	<i>Pinyaki</i>	<i>Vidari</i>	<i>Satavari</i>
<i>Mahati</i>	<i>Tarudha</i>	<i>Bisa</i>	<i>Saluka</i>	<i>Krauchandana</i>
<i>Kaseruka</i>	<i>Srungataka</i>	<i>Galodhya</i>	<i>Paushkarbeej</i>	<i>Tala</i>
<i>Munjataka</i>	<i>Sankha</i>	<i>Hastika</i>	<i>Raktanga</i>	<i>Madhu</i>

<i>Pindak</i>	<i>Srungakam</i>	<i>Pindaluka</i>	<i>Surendrakanda</i>	<i>Kadalikanda</i>
<i>Manaka</i>	<i>Surana</i>	<i>Bhukanda</i>	<i>Amlikakanda</i>	<i>Kumudakanda</i>
<i>Utpalakanda</i>	<i>Padmakanda</i>	<i>Musali</i>	<i>Varahkanda</i>	<i>Talashira</i>
<i>Nalikerashira</i>	<i>Kharjurashira</i>	<i>Bimbi</i>		

23-: *Srestha Varga*²⁵

Best among cereals (*Sastika, Yava, Godhuma, Lohita*) and pulses (*Mudga, Adhaki, Masura*), best among meat (*Ena, Harina, Kuranga* etc.) best among the fruit (*Dadima, Amalaka* etc.), best among the vegetables (*Chanchu, Satina, Vastuka*, etc.), and other best drugs in different groups are described in this *Varga*.

24-*Rasa Varga*²⁶

Properties of *Madhura, Amla, Lavana, Katu, Tikta* and *Kashaya Rasa* are described in this *Varga*.

25-*Manda Varga*²⁷

Laja and *Lajamanda, Vatyamanda*, other varieties of *Manda* and their properties and Preparation of *Manda* described in this *Varga*.

26-*Anna Varga*²⁸

Ahara Kalpana described here are-

Table No.29 List of *Dravyas* described into *Anna Varga*

<i>Peya</i>	<i>Vilepi</i>	<i>Yavagu</i>
<i>Manda</i>	<i>Payasa</i>	<i>Kshara</i>

27-*Panabhaksya Varga*²⁹

Various *Ahara Kalpana* like *Soopa, Shaka, Saktu, Mantha, Laja* etc. are described here.

28-*Anupana Varga*³⁰

Different *Anupana Dravyas*, selection of *Anupana* and importance of water as *Anupana*, importance of *Anupana*, *Anupana* for various diseases, importance of warm water as *Anupana*, *Anupana* for different drugs, various *Anupana* for various conditions, contraindications of *Anupana*, dose of *Anupana* in different conditions, importance of consumption of water in the morning and importance of consumption of *Haritaki* described in this *Varga*.

29-*Prakirna Varga*³¹

Swasthvrutt and *Dincharya* are described in this *Varga*.

Discussion:

Madhav Dravyaguna is written by *Madhav Kavi* in 14th century, *Nighantu* has 29 *Varga*. *Vividha Ausadhi Varga* includes all the *Ausadha dravyas* including herb and minerals. Minerals and animal products are described after herbs. It ends with description of *Puspa* (flowers) *Ausadha dravyas* having common therapeutic effects are arranged one after the other. Properties of Drugs having similar properties are also described together as *Prushnaparni* and *Sthira* while in other *Nighantu* both drugs are described separately with description of *Rasa*, *Guna* and *Roghaghata*. Properties of sugarcane based on the part like roots of *Iksu* are sweet in taste, internodes are sweet and the tips, nodes and bark are salty in taste; appearance of different types of honey and incompatibilities of honey are described. Appearance of different types of honey described here are- *Maksika* is similar in appearance to sesame oil (*Taila*), *Pauttika* appears like *Ghee* (*Ghruta*), *Ksaudra* is tawny brown in colour (*Kapila Varna*) and *Bhramara* is clear like crystal (*Sphatika*). Properties of the milk obtained from cows having different colours, properties of hot and cold milk, properties of milk consumed at different times of the day, properties of the milk collected during different times of the day are elaborately described. *Sneha Varga* is mentioned separately along with *ghruta* and *taila Varga*. *Kanjika Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Madya Varga*. *Matsya Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Mamsa Varga*.

Conclusion:

Presentation method of *Madhav Dravyaguna* is unique. Here, *Karma* of the *Dravya* is given prime importance for the sequential arrangement of *Dravyas*. Drugs having similar properties are described together and their *Rasapanchaka* or *Rogaghata* are not described separately. *Kshira* is described elaborately with its various properties. *Sneha Varga* is mentioned separately along with *ghruta* and *taila Varga*. *Kanjika Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Madya Varga*. *Matsya Varga* is mentioned separately along with *Mamsa Varga*, showcasing the different pattern of classification by *Madhav Kavi*.

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